

DEVELOPMENT OF A DESIGN MODEL FOR PERFORATED-RIB-TYPE SHEAR CONNECTORS IN A NOVEL COMPOSITE PLATE PERPENDICULAR TO THEIR AXIS

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ABSTRACT

The Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite-Plate (SCSC-Plate), which was devised as a more economical alternative to full-section steel plates as deck slabs for railway bridges, is currently being developed at TU Wien. This type of slab utilizes steel ribs with circular holes as shear connectors to enable the transfer of shear forces between the external steel chord plates through a concrete core.

Various aspects of the load bearing behavior of this new type of structural element have been investigated and partially characterized this far. However, the behavior of the structure perpendicular to the axis of the shear connectors (i. e. in the deck slab's secondary load bearing direction) has not been analyzed until now.

To create a design guideline for the SCSC-Plate, numerical simulations and empirical tests are being carried out. Using the obtained data, simplified modeling approaches can be proposed. These models currently range from the separate consideration of the behavior of the slab along the two axes to a more complex integrated approach using common FE-modeling software and multiple models of varying resolution.

This paper provides an overview of the development path of the design model for the load bearing direction perpendicular to the shear connectors when using a separate axes type of design approach. This model consists of a combination of varying strut-and-tie models for the reinforced concrete and beam elements for the structural steel components. The model was verified via comparison with a numerical model which was in turn verified using empirical data obtained from experimental tests.

Keywords: Bridge Structures, Composite Steel Structures, Modeling of Steel Structures

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

As older railway bridges are approaching the end of their service life, of which many are bridges with short spans, suitable replacement structures become necessary.

For certain applications bridge deck structures with a very low structural depth are required, particularly where there are clearance requirements below the bridge. Using a shallow bridge deck structure in these cases avoids having to raise the elevation of the railway line over a large section of track. (1)

For these applications full section steel slabs have been used. (2, 3) These are however somewhat structurally inefficient due to the under-utilized material around their center-plane when loaded primarily in bending. In addition, they can be both difficult to procure and to work with, especially when they need to be butt-welded.

The SCSC-plate is currently being developed at the Research Unit Steel Structures at TU Wien and was devised as a more economical alternative to these full section plates by replacing the central portion of the plate with a cheaper reinforced concrete core. (1, 4-7)

To make this proposed structural element applicable in bridge designs, design guidelines and design models need to be developed which allow designers to check for code compliance with a balance of limited computational expense and sufficient accuracy to ensure both the safety of the structure and an economical design.

1.2 Proposed Structure of the SCSC-Plate

The SCSC-Plate in its current state of development consists of two outer chord plates, which are anchored into the concrete core using perforated steel plate shear connectors. These plates are intended to be 15 mm and 20 mm thick respectively and made of S355 grade steel. The concrete is expected to be grade C40/50 combined with $\varnothing 20$ (main rebar) and $\varnothing 10$ (stirrups) reinforcement of grade B550. The main geometrical measurements of the structure are labeled in Fig. 2.

To make the low structural depth of the plate possible while also maintaining limited fabrication complexity, the plate is assembled from two partial steel cross-sections with alternately connected shear connectors, as shown in Fig. 1. The two partial steel cross sections are not directly welded to each other due to the lack of accessibility of the weld interfaces. Instead, a reinforced concrete core, in combination with the perforated shear connectors, enables the shear force transfer between the top and the bottom steel plate. The current iteration of this new kind of deck slab structure has a total height of 200 mm.

Fig. 1 Assembly process of the SCSC-Plate

The name of the SCSC-Plate is derived from the structure of the composite cross-section: Steel-Concrete-Steel-Composite Plate.

The main intended areas of application of the SCSC-Plate are the bottom chords of trough bridges and slab bridges with short spans, see Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Primary intended use cases of the SCSC-Plate: a) slab bridge for short spans; b) bottom chord of a trough bridge for short to medium spans

1.3 Scope of this contribution

This contribution presents the development path for a design model for the SCSC-Plate perpendicular to the shear connectors when using a structural analysis approach which includes designing for the load bearing behavior along separate axes (see section 2.1). The individual aspects of this development are outlined and summarized:

- Proposed structural analysis approach and design model for the load bearing behavior perpendicular to the shear connectors
- Application and usability when designing based on structural codes
- Verification and validation of the design model for the load bearing behavior perpendicular to the shear connectors using numerical models and experimental tests

Since the entire design guideline as well as certain elements of the proposed model are not finalized yet, any specifics are still subject to change and are not to be seen as representative design examples. For simplicity, the design approach is explained and examples refer to the case of the slab bridge (see *Fig. 2*).

2 DESIGN MODELING APPROACH

2.1 Structural Analysis Approach

In general, two types of design approaches were considered for the design model of the SCSC-Plate. First, an integrated modeling approach, which would mainly use a single, but more complex structural model to provide the majority of input parameters for code checks, with additional smaller models for specific structural details where necessary. Second, a separated design approach, in which internal forces are calculated using a comparatively simpler global model and input parameters for any necessary checks are obtained from several separate design models. In the proposed design approach specifically, the internal forces are calculated for the directions parallel and perpendicular to the shear connectors using a global model and are applied to design models for the load bearing behavior of the SCSC-Plate along these two axes. The obtained stresses and forces can then be superimposed to obtain the required results.

The integrated analysis approach entails more complex and intricate (FE-)models, which would be more computationally expensive, would require more specific software functionality and therefore more in-depth familiarity with the software from the designer. However, the resulting workflow may be more streamlined, and the results may lead to more economical designs.

The separated approach may be more familiar to designers, less computationally expensive and easier to implement for a given design project. On the other hand, more manual computations and analysis steps may be required and the results are likely to be more conservative and lead to less economical designs.

Both design approaches may be developed in the future, this contribution however covers the development of the design model for the axis perpendicular to the shear connectors in the case of the separated analysis approach.

All design models are being developed primarily with the code provisions of the Eurocode series 1, 2, 3 and 4 in mind. (8-11)

2.2 Proposed global structural model

The current iteration of the proposed global structural model, which is used to obtain internal forces in the slab, uses an orthotropic plate to represent the SCSC-Plate. Since the stiffness of the SCSC-Plate along the two axes is not sufficiently well known yet and may not be described accurately by a flexural stiffness alone, the flexural stiffness along the axis perpendicular to the shear connectors needs to be varied within certain bounds to avoid obtaining non-conservative results for following calculations.

The upper bound of this flexural stiffness is that of the two chord plates with an assumed rigid shear connection. This stiffness was determined to be accurate experimentally for the SCSC-Plate along

the axis parallel to the shear connectors (i. e. the primary load bearing direction) in the tests described in (5) and can be used along that axis for all considered combinations. Using this stiffness as an upper bound along the axis perpendicular to the shear connectors yields conservative internal forces along this secondary axis. As a lower bound, a flexural stiffness of zero may be assumed for conservative results along the axis parallel to the shear connectors. Alternatively, the flexural stiffness obtained from the test specimens described in section 3.2 may be used as the lower bound for the axis perpendicular to the shear connectors.

The obtained internal forces from the global model will then be used as inputs for the design models. For edge details and other irregularities refinements or adaptations of the model may be necessary. An example of a global design model and qualitative distributions of the internal forces for a slab bridge are shown in *Fig. 3*. The model consists of an orthotropic plate on two line supports, loaded with a constant load for the ballast bed and a live load according to EN 1991 (8) along a central strip in the direction of the span. In this case the design axes parallel and perpendicular to the shear connectors run parallel and perpendicular to the span direction, respectively.

Fig. 3 Example of the proposed global design model for a slab bridge (a) and distribution of internal forces (bending moments m; shear forces v) (b) (design axes parallel and perpendicular to the shear connectors abbreviated as paSC and peSC)

2.3 Proposed local design model for internal forces perpendicular to the shear connectors

To determine design stresses in the SCSC-Plate from internal forces along the axis perpendicular to the shear connectors, an engineering model has been developed.

This model consists of a template for variable strut-and-tie models for the reinforced concrete core connected to beam-elements representing the structural steel components of the SCSC-Plate, shown in *Fig. 4*. The main rebar running through the shear connectors is also modeled using beam elements. This model can be implemented in structural analysis software such that the individual members of the strut and tie model are iteratively activated or deactivated as required by the applied forces.

Fig. 4 Strut and tie model framework: a) steel and rebar elements only; b) template for concrete struts

When intended to be used as a design model as described above, at least three concrete core segments should be modeled. Design stresses may be obtained from the central segment, the outer segments should be viewed as load transmission areas with differing stress distributions from a continuous system. This configuration was determined to yield very similar results for the stress distributions to a model of an entire test specimen when loaded with the equivalent internal forces. Such a middle segment of the design model is shown in Fig. 5. Because the shear connectors are welded to the chord plates in an alternating pattern, either two different models need to be considered or one model with reversed loads to make the design independent of the exact location of the welds and internal force peaks. This is due to the different ways the shear force transfer across a concrete core segment can take place, depending on the configuration of the adjacent shear connectors and the direction of the shear force. This difference in the shear force transmission behavior then leads to differences in the stress distribution across various members of the model in the two cases.

Fig. 5 Load bearing behavior of the SCSC-Plate perpendicular to the shear connectors – concrete core segments in their shear truss (a) and wedging (b) configurations, depending on the orientation of the adjacent shear connectors relative to the orientation of the acting internal shear force

For element (a) in *Fig. 5* the shear force may be transferred across the middle segment in this model via compression struts between the two corners where the shear connectors are welded to the chord plates. In element (b) in *Fig. 5*, this is not possible since the shear connector cannot transfer a vertical tension force to the chord plate (since it is not welded to it). Instead, the design model proposes a strut-and-tie type shear transfer model between the two shear connectors and a wedging mechanism of the concrete segment. The concrete segment in the middle of element (b) would be rotated clockwise due to the forces acting on the inside of the two shear connectors, however the core segment's movement is restricted by the two adjacent segments and the chord plates. This mechanism is shown in a simplified form on the right in *Fig. 5*. An example of the active compression struts in two model variants for shear and flexural loading are shown in *Fig. 6*. In order to determine the bending stresses in the steel plates and the main rebar, which are required to check fatigue resistance provisions, these components are modeled using flexurally stiff beam elements. An example of the resulting stress distribution for a design model loaded in shear and flexure is shown in *Fig. 6*.

Fig. 6 Example results for a design model element loaded in shear and flexure:
a) stress distribution in the steel components and rebar elements; b) active concrete struts

2.4 Checking Compliance with Code Requirements

The stresses and stress ranges determined using the design models may be used as inputs for checking compliance with the relevant code requirements, specifically stress checks for steel components, stress range checks for fatigue requirements and stress limits for strut and tie models. Since the design model outputs stresses for the steel, rebar and concrete components, code checks may be performed relatively easily against fixed maximum values with comparatively little additional post-processing of the results.

Total design stresses for global checks may be obtained via superposition of stresses from the design model for internal forces perpendicular to the shear connectors described in this contribution and additional models for internal forces parallel to the shear connectors. These additional models are being developed separately and are not part of the work presented in this contribution.

Provisions which limit deflections or rotations may be checked using results from the global structural analysis model described in section 2.2.

3 VERIFICATION AND VALIDATION

3.1 Verification Strategy

To verify that the results obtained from the design models are either accurate or conservative, experimental tests were performed and analyses of three-dimensional nonlinear finite element models were conducted.

3.2 Experimental Tests

A test series using specimens shown in *Fig. 7* was conducted to investigate the load bearing behavior of a segment of the SCSC-Plate perpendicular to the shear connectors. This specimen represents a section of SCSC-Plate four shear connectors wide and six core segments long.

Fig. 7 Test specimen and test setup used to investigate the load bearing behavior of the SCSC-Plate perpendicular to the shear connectors

The experiments were conducted in a three-point bending configuration with the intent to test the shear force transfer across a core segment in the wedging configuration described in section 2.3.

The test specimens were first loaded cyclically at various load levels and specimens which showed no deterioration due to fatigue after at least two million load cycles were then tested statically to failure. The load levels for the cyclic tests were 4 kN to 120 kN, 4 kN to 168 kN, 4 kN to 216 kN and 64 kN to 406 kN, as well as 64 kN to 424 kN.

Only the two specimens tested at the highest load levels exhibited a failure due to fatigue. The specimens showed breaks in the main rebars at the first shear connectors from the center of the specimens' span, denoted by a very slight increase in the specimen's vertical deflection after each break. These rebar fractures however did not impact the specimens' capacity to carry the applied cyclic load. The rebar failures were later followed by the formation of a crack in the bottom chord plate next to the weld of the first shear connector from the center of the specimens' span. The tests were stopped after the discovery of these cracks to examine and disassemble the specimens, at which point the fractured reinforcement was found.

The failure points correlate well with the points of high tensile stress ranges in the numerical and design models, as shown in *Fig. 8*.

Fig. 8 Fatigue failure points in the test specimen: a) broken reinforcement and cracked chord plate; b) corresponding tensile stress peaks in the numerical simulation (top and middle) and corresponding tensile stress peaks in the design model (bottom)

Results of the seven static tests are shown in Fig. 9 below.

3.3 3D Finite Element Model

To better understand the experimental tests and verify the design models, a three-dimensional finite element model of the test specimen was created and analyzed in the FEA software ABAQUS.

For this application, the nonlinear concrete damaged plasticity model was used in combination with one dimensional embedded beam elements representing the reinforcement.

Preliminary results of this model are presented in Fig. 9.

3.4 Model Comparison and Conclusions

Overall, the models agree well with the experimental results at load levels which are likely to be relevant for the design of an SCSC-bridge deck. A comparison of preliminary results is presented in Fig. 9. While the resolution and accuracy of the numerical model could be improved further, it agrees reasonably well with experimental results at design load levels. The failure mode of the test specimen is also predicted well, as can be seen on the left in Fig. 9; however, this failure occurs prematurely in the model. The reason for the divergence of the results at higher loads may be investigated further in the future.

Fig. 9 Comparison of deformation and failure mode of the test specimen, FE-model and design model

The design model is included in the diagram in Fig. 9 for reference. It shows larger deflections than the experimental data and the numerical model. However, predicting deflections is not the goal or intended application of the design model as explained in section 2.4. The calculated stresses in the design model are all either very similar or err on the conservative side when compared to the numerical model at the approximate maximum FLS load level for a slab bridge with a span of 4,5 m. The predicted deflection for a linear elastic beam with the flexural stiffness of the two chord plates with an assumed rigid shear connection mentioned in section 2.3 is also included in the diagram for reference. This model predicts lower deflections than the test, which is at least in part attributed to the low shear stiffness of the wedging segment in the test. This behavior is qualitatively represented in both the numerical and design models.

From this comparison it can be concluded that the numerical model and in turn the design model (for its intended purpose) plausibly represent the experimental test at relevant design load levels. However, further verification, investigations and possibly calibrations of the model will be necessary before the model can be applied in bridge design projects.

Specifically, additional load configurations and combinations of internal forces should be analyzed to cover a sufficient range of the non-linear load bearing behavior of the SCSC-Plate. The design model can be adapted to additional reference data from tests or numerical analyses by changing the cross sections and specific geometry of the concrete struts as well as the stiffness of connections between the struts, ties and beam elements of the model (see Fig. 5). This way the design concept possesses some robustness and is adaptable to possible future discoveries and necessary changes in the development process of the design guideline for the SCSC-Plate.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

4.1 Summary

In summary, a proposed design concept has been laid out for the use of an SCSC-Plate as a bridge deck. An engineering model for the load bearing behavior perpendicular to the shear connectors was developed and in principle has been shown to be suitable as a design model. The results of the proposed design model were compared to results of a three-dimensional numerical model of a test specimen and verified for a selected load level. The numerical model was in turn validated via experimental tests of the chosen test specimens.

To generally verify the model, comparisons to reference results or test data for further load levels and combinations of internal forces are required. However, based on the presented results, the concept of using a template of strut and tie models in conjunction with beam elements and an iterative solver appears both sufficiently accurate and user-friendly as well as adaptable enough to future calibration data to be used as a design tool for the described application.

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